

Popular Article

Pet Associated Zoonoses

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Abstract

Pets are a growing part of families and share human lifestyles. An estimated 14% to 62% of pet owners let their dogs and cats sleep on their beds. However, such activities may be linked to dangers to the public's health, such as a rise in the emergence of zoonoses. The possibility of transmitting zoonotic agents by close contact between pets and their owners through bed sharing, kissing, or licking is significant and has even been documented for life-threatening infections, even though zoonotic infections acquired from a pet are uncommon.

Introduction

In almost every community and culture, having pets has served as a cultural and social need. Health, emotional, and social advantages are possible. Over 60% of families in the west are thought to have pets. In many nations, dogs and cats are the most commonly kept as pets. Pet-related zoonotic infections are quickly becoming a significant public health concern due to the rapid growth of the pet population. They are among the primary carriers and reservoirs of numerous zoonotic infections brought on by bacteria, fungi, viruses, protozoa, and helminthic disorders (Stull et al., 2015).

Pet associated pathogens

Although many pathogens can be transmitted from pets to people, the pathogens of greatest concern are described in the table.

	Pathogen	Animal species
Bacterial	<i>Bartonella</i> spp.	Cats, dogs
	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	Cats, dogs, reptiles, ferrets
	<i>Capnocytophaga canimorsus</i>	Cats, dogs
	<i>Chlamydophila psittaci</i>	Birds
	<i>Leptospira</i> spp.	Cats, dogs, rodents
	<i>Salmonella</i> species	Amphibians, reptiles, cats, dogs, rodents
	<i>Mycobacterium marinum</i>	Fish
	<i>Vibrio</i> spp.	Fish
	<i>Yersinia</i> spp.	Rodents, reptiles
Viral	Rabies	Cats, dogs, ferret
	Lymphocytic choriomeningitis	Rodents
Mycotic	Dermatophytes	Cats, dogs
	<i>Encephalitozoon cuniculi</i>	Lagomorphs
Parasitic	<i>Giardia</i> spp.	Cats, dogs, ferret, rodents
	Hookworms	Cats, dogs
	<i>Toxocara</i> spp.	Cats, dogs, ferret
	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	Cats
	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp.	Cats, dogs

Table: Pathogens transmitted from pets

Who is most at risk?

- Children younger than 5 yrs
- Adults older than 65 yrs
- People with weakened immune systems
- Pregnant women

Transmission

- Pets and humans coming into direct contact through bites, scratches, or skin or mucous membrane contact with animal saliva, urine, or other body fluids or secretions is one route of transmission of infections. For instance, bartonellosis is typically brought on by a cat scratch (cat claws can pick up faeces from infected fleas) or a flea bite. In the United States, animal bites result in more than 4.7 million cases, 0.3 million emergency visits, 10,000 hospitalizations, and 20 fatalities annually, with dogs accounting for 80–90% and cats for 5–15% of cases (Said *et al.*, 2022).
- Consuming food that has been contaminated with animal faeces. People who unintentionally ate food contaminated with animal faeces have been diagnosed with salmonellosis.
- Breathing in infected droplets or aerosols. Normally found in the upper respiratory tract of dogs and cats, *Bordetella bronchiseptica* spreads to humans through aerosol. Though extremely uncommon in humans, this pathogen can give dog owners pneumonia and upper respiratory infections.
- Bite of invertebrate vectors and arthropods: Despite the fact that pets normally do not directly spread arthropod-borne illnesses to humans (such as Lyme borreliosis, ehrlichiosis, and anaplasmosis), they do bring the zoonotic disease vectors, like as ticks and fleas, into close contact with humans, potentially raising the risk of infection (Ghasemzadeh and Namazi, 2015),

Prevention & Control

- Choosing the right pet and educating yourself on safe pet handling are critical steps in lowering this risk.
- Ensure pets remain healthy with regular veterinary visits and preventive care
- Keep litter boxes away from locations where food is prepared and eaten, like as kitchens.
- Animal contact surfaces such as cages and feeding areas should be cleaned and disinfected on a regular basis; freshly mixed diluted household bleach (1 part bleach to 32 parts water) or similar household disinfectants (e.g., quaternary ammonium compounds) are sufficient (Chomel, 2014).
- Wash hands after handling animals or their environment
- Promptly wash bites and scratches caused by animals
- Keep pets away from open wounds, cuts, and medical equipment (such intravascular catheters); you should also prevent them from licking the faces of infants and patients with compromised immune systems.
- When cleaning up animal waste and its surroundings, wear gloves.

Conclusions

Patients with compromised immune systems, pregnant women, young children, and older persons are most at risk for illness transmission when pets are involved. Disease risk can be decreased through proper pet care, personal hygiene practices, and pet selection (species, age). With the use of the available information, doctors and other healthcare professionals can advise patients on responsible pet ownership and contact to lower the risk of pet-associated disease.

References

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